

MANC HIST

Community Fund Spotlight: Manchester Histories

Posted on: [3 Sep 2024](#) Last updated on: 9 Oct 2024 Categorized in: [Project Blog](#) Written by: [Ewan Hannaford](#)

MANCHESTER HISTORIES

[Manchester Histories](#) is a charity that works closely with [Archives+](#), a partnership of archive and local history organisations based at [Manchester Central Library](#). As a collaborating organisation working with *Our Heritage Our Stories*, Manchester Histories ran four excellent workshops facilitated by their Community Archivist, Rhianna Arnold. These events supported their mission to reveal, share, and celebrate the diverse histories and heritage of Greater Manchester, and to explore their approaches to Community Generated Digital Content (CGDC). Rhianna's data capture skills and the rich amount of Manchester-based material waiting to be made discoverable formed the basis of the workshops she organised, which benefited both the community groups who took part and provided an important opportunity to analyse their detailed metadata for *Our Heritage Our Stories* as part of designing our CGDC data models.

After the workshops were complete, Rhianna interviewed members of the community groups who took part to get more detailed information about their creation, management and use of CGDC. Her findings were published as part of a final report which outlines recommendations from the groups that the OHOS team are working into key project outputs, including our White Paper 'Saving UK CGDC at Risk', our Post-Custodial toolkit, and the design of our OHOS Observatory. This blog post provides a summary of the report and its findings.

Community archives in scope for Manchester Histories data gathering and workshops

[Greater Manchester Coalition for Disabled People](#) (GMCDP), [Manchester Digital Music Archive](#) (MDMA), [Park Friends](#) and [Manchester Hip Hop Archive](#) all participated in the Manchester Histories workshops. Each organisation has unique characteristics and aims that influence the way they handle their digital content and how it needs to be accessed online.

Greater Manchester Coalition for Disabled People (GMCDP) documents and preserves the history and narratives of their own organisation as well as the [Disabled Peoples' Movement](#). It is committed to democratic control of materials by its members while ensuring widespread access to its vast digital collection that include photographs, banners, posters, campaign materials, and much more.

Manchester Digital Music Archive celebrates Greater Manchester's varied musical heritage, focusing on uncovering lesser-known music scenes and amplifying the voices of underrepresented communities. It prioritises digitising vulnerable collections and raising public awareness of these.

Volunteers play a vital role in **Park Friends**, a charity promoting the preservation, restoration, maintenance, and improvement of [Platt Fields Park](#). It is therefore crucial that digital training initiatives are organised to ensure that the maintenance of their online platforms can be sustained as volunteers come and go.

Manchester Hip Hop Archive is an online platform that preserves and shares the city's influential hip-hop history. It aims to bridge the digital gap between younger and older artists, ensuring that the legacy of local hip-hop trailblazers remains accessible for future generations.

The diverse aims of each community-driven initiative provide a holistic perspective of the challenges community groups might face when handling their digital content. Wide-ranging accessibility of their historical resources, inclusivity of narratives from underrepresented groups, engagement and collaboration with both communities and researchers were the key priorities of all four groups.

Challenges identified by the community archives

The groups identified several issues when trying to preserve their community-generated digital content and raised some concerns about how a unified online platform displaying their materials might impact their role:

- Digital Platform Problems:** Groups noted accessibility issues that, at times, limited their ability to embrace a variety of digital tools and platforms. Some platforms were tricky to navigate, and the groups found it difficult to determine whether their materials would be discoverable.
- Expectations of researchers:** Many of us in the archive sector are aware of how interlinked the archive's role is in supporting academic researchers and historians. It is therefore unsurprising that expectations around accessibility of archival materials are high. These expectations, however, normally surpass what the groups can deliver to researchers as the majority are made up of volunteers or part-time staff with limited time and resources.
- Community Archives Autonomy:** For all the groups, maintaining autonomy over their unique collections is of paramount importance. While their individuality is important, so is ensuring that they are also handling logistical issues such as copyright, ownership, and technical issues linked to their materials correctly, especially if they are to be published on a national platform.
- Visibility:** The community archives questioned whether making their materials available within a larger archival ecosystem might undermine or overshadow their own efforts.

Whilst acknowledging the many challenges they faced with digital archives, the community groups that Rhianna spoke to were positive about the possibility of a unified public-facing platform. They were keen to embrace opportunities for greater recognition, engagement, and discoverability. The groups kindly offered recommendations to OHOS to ensure that any platform used to transition our national records towards a more democratic collection, or to preserve community held data, would remain true to the intentions of the groups that created these materials.

So, while the idea of a unified hub for sharing materials is welcomed, community groups highlighted that **producing highly accessible content** should be the priority. Community archives value their unique user experiences which best serve their communities and want to be part of a larger archival community at the same time as maintaining their distinct identities.

Each of the community archives Rhianna consulted offer a rich diversity of materials, underscoring their commitment to inclusivity and empowering individuals to share their histories. These initiatives deserve recognition and their contents should be considered on a par with that of other repositories.

[Previous Post WCIA MayDay Archiveathon](#)

[Next Post Community Archives and Heritage Group Conference 2024](#)

